
Discrete and continuous approaches for the failure analysis of masonry structures subjected to settlements

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Numerical modelling of masonry structures is nowadays still an active research field, given a
4 number of open issues related to preservation and restoration of historical constructions and the
5 availability of computational tools that have become more and more refined. This work focuses
6 on the analysis of settlement-induced failure patterns characterizing the in plane response of two-
7 dimensional dry-joints masonry panels, which differ in terms of texture, geometry and settlement
8 configuration. Brick-block masonry, interpreted as a jointed assembly of prismatic particles in
9 dry contact, can be modelled as a discrete system of rigid blocks interacting through contact
10 surfaces with no tensile strength and finite friction, modelled as zero thickness elasto-plastic
11 Mohr-Coulomb interfaces. Different approaches and numerical models are adopted herein: Limit
12 Analysis (LA), a discrete model DEM and a continuous Finite Element Model (FEM). Limit
13 Analysis is able to provide fast and reliable results in terms of collapse multiplier and relative
14 kinematics. In this work, a standard LA procedure is coded through Linearised Mathematical
15 Programming to take into account sliding mechanisms through dilatant joints. Discrete models are
16 particularly suitable to study historical masonry materials, where rigid bodies interact between
17 contact and friction. Here, a combined Finite/Discrete Element approach (FEM/DEM) is adopted.
18 Finally, analyses are conducted through the Finite Element approach, resorting to a continuum
19 anisotropic elastic-perfectly plastic constitutive model. Some selected case-studies have been
20 investigated adopting the above mentioned models and numerical results have been interpreted
21 to highlight the capability of the approaches to predict failure patterns for various geometrical
22 features of the structure and settlement configurations.

23 **Keywords:** Limit Analysis, FEM/DEM, Finite Element, Masonry Structures, Rigid Blocks, Settlements.

1 INTRODUCTION

24 Masonry is one of the most ancient structural material and constitutes a vast majority of the World's
25 architectural heritage. It is a composite and heterogeneous medium, resulting from the assemblage of
26 natural or artificial blocks by means of mortar layers or dry joints. Being characterized by an internal

27 structure, which reflects in a complex mechanical response, masonry and its constitutive behaviour still
28 represent a challenging research field. Thanks to the availability of more and more powerful computational
29 resources, during last decades a large number of numerical applications have been developed, resorting
30 to different constitutive assumptions and solution algorithms. Nonetheless, it is not possible to state that
31 each of these models suits any structural problem, but their applicability needs to be evaluated case by
32 case, on the basis of geometrical features, extent of the structure and boundary conditions. Among the
33 available numerical modelling techniques for masonry structures, a broad distinction can be made between
34 micromechanical, macromechanical and multiscale models.

35 According to micromodeling strategy, the constituents, that is units, mortar (if present) and unit/mortar
36 interfaces, are separately modelled and each part is assigned a properly calibrated constitutive law. This
37 approach is particularly suitable if the response of the assemblage needs to be accurately described (Lotfi
38 and Shing (1994); Lourenço and Rots (1997); Oliveira and Lourenço (2004); Alfano and Sacco (2006);
39 Serpieri et al. (2017)), but a major hindrance is still represented by its high computational cost, consequence
40 of the large number of degrees of freedom needed to describe the structural configuration (Clementi et al.,
41 2019, 2020). In addition, the adopted constitutive assumptions often imply the calibration of a large set of
42 parameters which are not always easily determined.

43 Following a macromechanical approach, the heterogeneous medium is modelled as a continuum and the
44 constitutive behaviour is usually described through phenomenologically based mathematical relations, in
45 which degrading phenomena are accounted through damage or friction variables. In this case, macroscopic
46 mechanical properties are more easily derived from standard experimental tests on small masonry specimens.
47 These models are, if compared to micromechanical ones, more efficient from a computational point of
48 view (Del Piero, 1989; Gambarotta and Lagomarsino, 1997; Roca et al., 2005; Sangirardi et al., 2019a) and
49 are widely used for real-scale applications in which, depending on the complexity of the geometry of the
50 structure, different discretization strategies might result in the adoption of monodimensional, bidimensional
51 or three-dimensional finite elements.

52 Multiscale, i.e. micro-macro, continuum models represent a very promising approach for the analysis of
53 masonry structures since they can accurately keep track of the the mechanical and geometrical properties of
54 the material at the microstructure with a reduced computational cost if compared to a fully micromechanical
55 model (Masiani and Trovalusci, 1996; Trovalusci et al., 2010; Leonetti et al., 2018; Reccia et al., 2018).
56 These models are often derived by considering two material scales: a microscale where, having deduced
57 the mechanical properties of the components through experimental tests, a material representative volume
58 element (RVE) is defined and a macroscale structural level, where a homogeneous continuum is obtained
59 by performing a homogenization procedure based on the solution of boundary conditions problems for
60 the RVE (Addessi et al., 2018, 2016; Greco et al., 2016, 2017). Other multiscale strategies make use of
61 different homogenization techniques based on the so-called Cauchy rule and its generalizations (Capecchi
62 et al., 2011) allowing the derivation of generalized continua such as micropolar continua able to properly
63 represent scale effects, that in masonry materials are significant (Masiani and Trovalusci, 1996; Trovalusci
64 and Masiani, 2003; Pau and Trovalusci, 2012; Fantuzzi et al., 2019; Leonetti et al., 2019).

65 Due to their characteristics, masonry constructions have proven to be particularly vulnerable not only to
66 earthquakes but also to structural settlements. Cracking and damage, in fact, often occur as a consequence
67 of ground movements. In urban areas, this phenomenon is related to the realization of underground
68 infrastructures or, more in general, to anthropic triggering factors, while natural hazards (as for example
69 slow-moving landslides, liquefaction or consolidation processes) are more likely to interfere with masonry
70 constructions in rural areas. In both cases the understanding of the phenomenon and its description are

71 fundamental to identify the causes as well as to prevent the effects with appropriate protection measures,
 72 for modern and, moreover, for historical constructions. Several approaches for the prediction of settlement-
 73 induced damage may be found in the literature, that consider masonry either as an assembly of discrete
 74 blocks (DeJong, 2016; Portioli and Cascini, 2016) or as a continuum medium (Burd et al., 2000; Amorosi
 75 et al., 2014). The comparison between discrete and continuous models is also a widespread topic (Casalegno
 76 et al., 2013; Zampieri et al., 2019; Landolfo et al., 2020).

77 In this work, three modelling techniques are adopted to describe settlement induced crack patterns in
 78 masonry panels characterized by different geometrical configurations and boundary conditions, reproducing
 79 the ground movement as a downward moving rigid block. Limit Analysis, largely recognized as a very
 80 effective tool to estimate collapse load and collapse mechanisms for masonry structures (Baggio and
 81 Trovalusci, 2000; Milani, 2011; Portioli et al., 2014; Pepe et al., 2019b; Milani and Taliercio, 2016;
 82 Pavlovic et al., 2016; Cascini et al., 2018), is used to determine the failure configuration of dry joints
 83 masonry panels subjected to settlements, modelling the walls (according to the microscale approach) as an
 84 assemblage of rigid blocks in contact through frictional interfaces.

85 The results of the analyses, performed on panels, walls with openings and facades, are compared with the
 86 ones obtained through a FEM/DEM approach (Baraldi et al., 2018) and with those obtained by means of a
 87 continuum (macroscale) Finite Element approach, adopting an elasto-plastic anisotropic constitutive model
 88 (Lasciarrea et al., 2019; Sangirardi et al., 2019b). In the following, the main features of the models are
 89 recalled in Section 2, the selected case-studies and the results of the analyses are then presented in Section
 90 3 and critically compared in order to highlight the influence of walls aspect ratio, width of the settling area
 91 and presence of openings. Finally in Section 4 some remarks and future developments are reported.

2 ADOPTED MICROMODELS

92 2.1 Rigid block model for limit analysis

93 The first adopted model is framed within the Limit Analysis (LA) theory, taking into account the presence
 94 of friction. The model considers as a system of n rigid blocks directly interacting through m contact
 95 surfaces unable to carry tension and resistant to sliding by friction. The blocks can translate and rotate
 96 about the edges of the contact surfaces (hinging) as well as sliding along the joints.

97 In order to provide the mechanical details of the model, let consider two simple blocks represented in Figure
 98 1a, introducing $\underline{e}_i = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}^T$ the orthonormal basis in the three-dimensional space. Loads are applied
 99 to the centroid of each rigid block i -th: static 'dead' loads are collected in vector $\underline{f}_0^i = \{f_{01}^i, f_{02}^i, m_{03}^i\}^T$,
 100 live loads are collected in the vector $\underline{f}_L^i = \{f_{L1}^i, f_{L2}^i, m_{L3}^i\}^T$. For the whole structure it results $\underline{f}_0 = \{\underline{f}_0^i\}$
 101 and $\underline{f}_L = \{\underline{f}_L^i\}$, with $i = 1, \dots, n$. The vector of the load over the whole system is $\underline{f} = \underline{f}_0 + \alpha \underline{f}_L$,
 102 where live loads are proportional to the dead loads through a non-negative coefficient, α , called collapse
 103 multiplier. Let $\underline{u}^i = \{u_1^i, u_2^i, \theta_3^i\}$ denote the vector of generalized displacement of the centroid of each
 104 i -th block. The vector $\underline{u} = \{\underline{u}^i\}$, with $i = 1, \dots, n$, collects the displacement for the whole structure
 105 which correspond in a virtual work sense to loads \underline{f} .

106 The static variables are the internal forces acting at each j -th contact surface between blocks, that is
 107 the normal force N^j , the shear force T^j and the moment M^j . For each joint they are collected in vector
 108 $\underline{\sigma}^j = \{N^j, T^j, M^j\}^T$. The vector $\underline{\sigma} = \{\underline{\sigma}^j\}$, with $j = 1, \dots, m$, refers to the whole structure.

109 The kinematic variables, or generalized strain, are the relative displacement rates at joints, that is normal
 110 displacement ξ^j , tangential displacement γ^j and rotation χ^j . For each joint $j = 1, \dots, m$ they are collected

111 in the vector $\varepsilon^j = \{\xi^j, \gamma^j, \chi^j\}^T$. The vector $\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon^j\}$ refers to the whole structure and corresponds in a
 112 virtual work sense to the vector of static variables σ .

Figure 1. a) Simple two-blocks structure b) Displacement components for a rigid block c) Model for settlement: panel with fictitious block

112
 113 The kinematic compatibility for the whole system is expressed by equation

$$\varepsilon = B u , \tag{1}$$

114 where B represents the compatibility matrix defined in (Baggio and Trovalusci, 2000).

115 The equilibrium of the whole structure is defined by the equation

$$B^T \sigma + f = 0 . \tag{2}$$

116 The generalized yield domain of the system can be written as

$$y = N^T \sigma \leq 0 , \tag{3}$$

117 where N is the block-diagonal gradient matrix referred to the adopted failure surface.

118 The flow rule expresses the vector ε as a linear combination of non-negative coefficients λ , called inelastic
 119 multiplier, and it can be written as

$$\varepsilon = M \lambda . \tag{4}$$

120 The plastic behavior of contact surfaces is defined through the complementarity condition

$$\lambda^T y = 0 . \tag{5}$$

121 Furthermore, the non-negative work of the live loads which cause the collapse mechanism is defined by the
122 following equation

$$\mathbf{f}_L^T \mathbf{u} = 1 . \quad (6)$$

123 In (Baggio and Trovalusci, 2000) the authors presented a home-made code, *ALMA* (Analisi Limite Murature
124 Attrittive) based on a two-step procedure, to deal with the non-linear and non-convex programming
125 problem (NLNCP) related to the presence of frictional interfaces (non-standard LA) of bidimensional and
126 threedimensional block masonry structures.

127 As reported in (Pepe et al., 2019a,b), following the approach in (Baggio and Trovalusci, 2000), a new
128 version of the code, *ALMA 2.0*, was implemented using *MATLAB*[®] for linear optimization and a *Python*TM
129 interface for pre and post processing operations. In particular, this new version is based on the kinematic
130 approach of Limit Analysis and considers for sliding a linearized behaviour of joints. This aspect is
131 significant because the computational effort due to the solution of the NLNCP is avoided. Indeed, the
132 advantage of a linear mathematical programming technique, deriving by the presence of the dilatant
133 behaviour of the contact surfaces, can provide a unique and quite fast solution of the problem.

134 Here, the optimization problem presented in (Pepe et al., 2019b) has been modified to include the
135 presence of settlements into the model (Pepe, 2020). A preliminary modification of the model has been the
136 introduction of the possibility to add kinematic constraints to the block of the structure. The displacement
137 components of every points of a generic *i*th block have been expressed as function of the displacement
138 components of its center of gravity. Let consider a generic point A of the *i*th block shown in Figure 1b.
139 Equation of rigid motion, describing its horizontal, vertical and rotation movement are reported as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_1^A &= u_1^G - \theta_3^G h_{v,i} , \\ \hat{u}_2^A &= u_2^G + \theta_3^G h_{o,i} , \\ \hat{\theta}_3^A &= \theta_3^G , \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

140 assumed in a compact form as

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{u} , \quad (8)$$

141 where, for the whole structure, the matrix \mathbf{V} contains the geometrical information of the points where the
142 kinematical constraints are inserted. In particular, the components of displacement $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ became identically
143 null depending on the typology of the external constraint considered. The modified programming problem,
144 considering the expression of \mathbf{u} wrote as function of the inelastic multiplier λ , is represented by

$$\begin{aligned} \min \alpha &= -\boldsymbol{\lambda}^T (\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{N}_1)^T \mathbf{f}_0 \text{ subjected to} \\ (\mathbf{A} \mathbf{N}_1 - \mathbf{N}_2) \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \mathbf{0} , \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T (\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{N}_1)^T \mathbf{f}_L - 1 &= 0 , \\ \mathbf{V} \mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{N}_1 \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \mathbf{0} , \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda} &\geq \mathbf{0} , \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

145 where introducing \mathbf{B}_1 , that is the kinematical submatrix of maximum rank and \mathbf{B}_2 the rest of the kinematical
146 matrix, the matrix \mathbf{A}_0 is the inverse of \mathbf{B}_1 . The matrix is defined as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{B}_2 \mathbf{B}_1^{-1}$ and \mathbf{N} is the transpose
147 of block-diagonal gradient matrix ($\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{N}_1, \mathbf{N}_2]$).

148 Following the idea of (Portioli and Cascini, 2016), in order to introduce a local foundation settlement into
 149 the model, the mathematical and geometrical formulation of the model has been modified with the addition
 150 of a fictitious rigid block, with degrees of freedom associated to the imposed movement. In Figure 1c an
 151 example of the modified geometric model for a simple masonry panel is shown, indicating in yellow the
 152 fictitious rigid block.

153 Another difference introduced into the model concerns the definition of the loads applied to the blocks.
 154 Indeed, in that case, every block of the structure is subjected only to its dead load, while live load is
 155 applied only on the block that simulate the settlement. In details, for that block, dead load is an upward
 156 force assumed proportional to an admissible base reaction without foundation settlement, considering a
 157 uniform distribution of vertical loads in the structure and denoted as $f_{(0,r)}$ while live load f_L is a downward
 158 force equal to dead load $f_{(0,r)}$ and proportional to the collapse multiplier α . Figure 1c shows the loading
 159 condition for the support block. The optimization problem has been changed taking advantage from the
 160 previously modification developed to include kinematic constraints. Indeed the displacement components
 161 of any point of the fictitious block \hat{u}_s are related to displacement components of the centroid u_s by means
 162 a matrix S that plays the same role of matrix V introduced for kinematic constraints

$$\hat{u}_s = S u_s . \quad (10)$$

163 It is consequently possible to particularize the movement of the support block u_s using the components
 164 described by the vector \hat{u}_s . Indeed, depending on the desired typology of settlement, some of its components
 165 could be imposed identically null. If for example the fictitious block have to move vertically, user have
 166 to put equal to zero only the horizontal and rotation components. The modified programming problem,
 167 considering the expression of u_s wrote as function of the inelastic multiplier λ , is represented by Eq. 9

$$\begin{aligned} \min \alpha = & -\lambda^T (A_0 N_1)^T f_0 \text{ subjected to} \\ & (A N_1 - N_2) \lambda = 0 , \\ & \lambda^T (A_0 N_1)^T f_L - 1 = 0 , \\ & S A_0 N_1 \lambda = 0 , \\ & \lambda \geq 0 . \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

168 2.2 Combined Finite/Discrete Element Model

169 A discrete model, made by means of a combined Finite-Discrete Element Model (FEM/DEM) approach,
 170 is here adopted.

171 Discrete Element Models (DEM) (Cundall, 1988) are a specific class of discrete models in which distinct
 172 elements can move independently, can come in or loose contact with other elements (the contact detection
 173 is governed by a molecular algorithm) and large displacements are considered.(Cundall and Hart, 1992).
 174 DEM are suitable to study non-linear problems characterized by the mutual movement of rigid bodies
 175 interacting by means of both contact and friction, such as jointed rock and granular assemblies (Cundall
 176 and Strack, 1979), and recently have been adopted for masonry modelling (Lemos, 2007; Cecchi and Sab,
 177 2004, 2009; Baraldi et al., 2015a).

178 In order to describe the deformability of the elements, simple FE discretizations have been proposed since
 179 the beginning of the development of DE Method (Cundall et al., 1985). Here, the combined FEM/DEM
 180 approach proposed by Munjiza (Munjiza, 2004) and developed by the Toronto Geo Group (Mahabadi

181 et al., 2010) is adopted. The approach relies in a combination of FEM and DEM: DEs are meshed into
 182 FEs with embedded crack elements that activate whenever the peak strength is reached. In this way, elastic
 183 deformation in the continuum is accounted by FEs, while interaction, fracture and fragmentation processes
 184 are modelled by DEs.

185 The FEM/DEM approach here adopted has been successfully adopted for masonry structures by some of
 186 the authors (Reccia et al., 2012; Baraldi et al., 2013, 2015b; Reccia et al., 2016; Baraldi et al., 2018; Reccia
 187 et al., 2018; Baraldi et al., 2019; Pepe et al., 2019a,b) and by other research groups (Smoljanović et al.,
 188 2013, 2015, 2017).

189 Numerical analyses are performed through the open source computer codes Y2D/Y-GUI (Mahabadi et al.,
 190 2010) and Y-Geo (Mahabadi et al., 2012), while input and results have been processed by means of CAD,
 191 ad-hoc *MATLAB*[®] scripts and spreadsheets.

192 A mesh of triangular CST FEs is made to model the specimens, under the hypothesis of plane stress.
 193 Masonry is modelled as an assemblage of rigid bricks, adopting a very high value of Young's Modulus
 194 and avoiding cracks inside the. Cracking may occur only in the joints between the bricks, modelled as
 195 zero-thickness Mohr-Coulomb interfaces, with only friction and no cohesion.

196 **2.3 FEM**

197 The third approach adopted to analyse failure mechanisms characterizing the response to settlements
 198 of masonry constructions is a continuum finite element (FE) one. The constitutive model, implemented
 199 in the FE code *PLAXIS 3D*[®], is a three-dimensional anisotropic elastic-perfectly plastic one. It stems
 200 from the Jointed Rock Model, and it has been enriched considering block aspect ratio and staggering joints
 201 effects. The Jointed Masonry Model (Lasciarrea et al., 2019) is characterized by isotropic elasticity and
 202 anisotropic yielding and can be included in the class of multi-laminates models (Pietruszczak and Niu,
 203 1992). Macroscopic elastic properties of the continuum are derived from the joints and blocks ones through
 204 a homogeneization procedure (De Buhan and de Felice, 1997; de Felice et al., 2010) and an equivalent
 205 isotropic behaviour can also be assumed assigning the material an average elastic modulus E as in the
 206 presented case-studies. A set of (maximum) three sliding directions, on which failure is meant to occur, is
 207 defined in the xyz space and described by means of *dip* (α_1) and *strike* (α_2). These parameters represent,
 208 for each plane, the positive rotation along the x -axis and the negative rotation along the z -axis respectively.
 209 In case of masonry panels with regular texture, these angles can be easily defined according to Figure 2. In
 210 the proposed examples, only two planes (head and bed joints) are activated, while a third plane might be
 211 considered in case of walls with double facing. Yield functions are defined, for each orientation, in terms
 212 of local stress components according to Coulomb's and tensile criterion as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i^c &= |\tau_i| + \sigma_{n,i} \tan \phi_i - c_i \\ f_i^t &= \sigma_{n,i} - \sigma_{t,i} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

213 where $i = 1,2,3$ is the plane *id*, $\sigma_{n,i}$ and τ_i are the normal and the shear stress along each orientation, ϕ_i is
 214 the friction angle, c_i is the cohesion and $\sigma_{t,i}$ is the tensile strength along the joints. The interlocking effect
 215 is accounted by modifying the strength parameters on the head-joints plane, stemming from equilibrium
 216 conditions and considering the aspect ratio of the blocks through the parameter β , which also depends on
 217 the friction angle of the bed joints:

$$\beta = \tan \phi_2 \frac{b}{2a} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. JMM bed and head joint plane orientation.

218 Tensile strength and cohesion on the head joints are hence:

$$\sigma_{t,1} = \sigma_{t0,1} - \beta \sigma_{n,2} + c_{0,2} \frac{\beta}{\tan \phi_2} \tag{14}$$

$$c_1 = c_{0,1} - \left(\beta \sigma_{n,2} - c_{0,2} \frac{\beta}{\tan \phi_2} \right) \tan \phi_1$$

and the modified strength criterion is reported in Figure 3. Table 1 reports the parameters adopted in the

Figure 3. Modified Mohr-Coulomb criterion.

219 analyses. An associated flow rule for plasticity has been assumed, but different values of dilatancy ψ_i can,
 220 in principle, be defined.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSES

222 The models have been validated using as benchmark the experimental and numerical results obtained by
 223 (Portioli and Cascini, 2016) who studied the collapse of different wall masonry panels made of dry jointed
 224 tuff blocks subjected to settlements. The test set-up has been designed *ad-hoc*, allowing a downward
 225 displacement of a portion of the structure, being the rest of the wall simply supported. Block dimensions

Test-id	G	ν	β	$c_{0,i}$	ϕ_i	ψ_i	$\sigma_{t,i}$	γ
Test 8C-12C	477 MPa	0.12	0.8	0 MPa	21.8°	21.8°	0 MPa	12 kN/m ³
Panel 1-5, Facade 1-3	511 MPa	0.12	0.4	0 MPa	21.8°	21.8°	0 MPa	12 kN/m ³

Table 1. Model parameters, 2D dry masonry walls subjected to settlements.

226 are equal to 100×200×50 mm³, the two walls are 1100 mm wide, 100 mm thick and differ in terms of
 227 height, since Test 8C is made of eight courses resulting in 400 mm height, while Test 12C is made of 12
 courses (600 mm height).

Figure 4. a) Experimental and b) numerical results for Test 8C. Modified from (Portioli and Cascini, 2016).

Figure 5. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Test 8C.

228

229 Figure 4 shows the experimental and numerical benchmark results producing a mechanism characterized
 230 by three macro-blocks: a first one, which behaves as a rigid block, at the left bottom side of the panel;
 231 a central one that rotates around the outer right vertex of the first macro-block, in which the blocks are
 232 subjected to sliding and rocking; a third macro-block that is separated by the others through a ‘stair-stepped’
 233 path and lies on the moving support. Figure 5 presents the collapse mechanism obtained with the different
 234 models referring to Test 8C. Figure 5a) and Figure 5b) present the mechanism of collapse obtained with
 235 LA and FEM/DEM. Both mechanisms agree with experimental and numerical results obtained by Portioli,
 236 producing a collapse where the three macro-blocks previously described can be easily identified. Figure
 237 5c) reports the distribution of the plastic points (blue points indicate tensile failure while grey points
 238 localize shear failure points). According to the typically observed crack patterns in case of *long* settlement
 239 (Mastrodicasa, 1958), tensile failure points are concentrated on the top part of the wall, while shear failure
 240 point are located along a 45° oriented direction going through the panel.

Figure 6. a) Experimental and b) numerical results for Test 12C. Modified from (Portioli and Cascini, 2016).

Figure 7. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Test 12C.

241 Figure 6 shows the experimental and numerical benchmark results producing a mechanism characterized
 242 by two macro-blocks separated by a ‘stair-stepped’ crack: the first macro-block, which is supported by
 243 the fixed base, and the second one, translating downwards on the movable support. Figure 7 presents
 244 the failure mechanisms obtained with the different models for Test 12C. Figure 7a) and 7b) present the
 245 mechanism obtained with LA and FEM/DEM which result in perfect accordance with experimental as
 246 well as numerical results obtained by the author. Indeed also in this case, the two macro-blocks previously
 247 described are easily distinguishable. Figure 7c) refers to continuum FEM modelling. The plastic point
 248 distribution is the one at failure, i.e. once the vertical reaction at the base of the moving support is constant,
 249 and if compared to the Test 8C case, less tensile plastic points can be observed. Nonetheless it has to
 250 be remarked that the adopted continuum approach allows to follow the entire settlement process and its
 251 evolution. In case of *shorter* settlement, shear failure first appears at the lower right corner of the wall, and
 252 the upper part of the panel is involved only in the last stages of the analysis. Conversely in case of Panel 8C
 253 the first plastic points to appear were the tensile ones in the upper portion of the specimen.

254 3.1 Square panels with opening

255 After this first validation, some geometries of masonry walls with openings or façades are analysed under
 256 settlement conditions involving a portion of the structure.

257 Two identical dry joints masonry walls, named Panel 1 and Panel 2, characterized by the presence of
 258 an opening are considered. The panels are constituted by 55 blocks having dimensions $50 \times 100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$
 259 and are 600 mm wide, 50 mm thick and 550 mm high; opening dimensions are $300 \times 250 \text{ mm}^2$. They
 260 differ in terms of length of the settling area, namely $200 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for Panel 1 and $300 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ for Panel
 261 2; the effect of this feature is here investigated with the three approaches. Figure 8 presents the collapse
 262 mechanism obtained with the different models, referring to Panel 1. LA, Figure 8a), and FEM/DEM, 8b),
 263 show a fragile behavior, with the macro-block (1) cracking into several parts some rotating other sliding,

Figure 8. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Panel 1 case.

264 the portion upon the architrave (2) slides while the macro-block upon the fictitious block (3) follows its
 265 downward movement cracking into several portions, which rotate and slide. 8c) reports the plastic points
 266 distribution at collapse obtained with the FEM approach. Tensile failure points are located at the top of the
 267 panel and at the lower right corner of the architrave, which is here modelled as an elastic element. The
 268 configuration described by this plastic point distribution is in good agreement with the results of the LA
 269 and FEM/DEM analysis.

Figure 9. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Panel 2 case.

270 Figure 9 presents the collapse mechanism of Panel 2, obtained with the different models.

271 LA and FEM/DEM, 9a) and 9b), exhibit the formation of three distinct macro-blocks divided by ‘stair-
 272 stepped’ cracks: a first one remains stable (1), a second one represented by the portion upon the architrave
 273 rotates around the upper right corner of the first block and a third portion of the wall (3) follows, without
 274 crashing, the downward movement of the fictitious block.

275 FEM results, presented in terms of plastic points distribution (Figure 9c), show that the overall collapse
 276 mechanism is affected by the length of the settlement only in the supported part of the wall, while in the
 277 top part, as in the other two approaches, cracking is located at the corners.

278 3.2 Slender panels with opening

279 In the following analyses the effect of settlement configuration is investigated together with the influence
 280 of wall height and presence of openings. Three slender panels, characterized by different height and number
 281 of openings, named Panel 3, Panel 4 and Panel 5, have been studied. Dimensions of blocks are $50 \times 100 \times 50$
 282 mm^3 for all the specimens and the openings are $100 \times 250 \text{ mm}^2$ wide. Panel 3 and Panel 4 are both made
 283 of 73 blocks and have the same dimensions, that is 400 mm width, 50 mm thickness and 900 mm height,
 284 but they differ because of the extension of the portion involved in the settlement. The fictitious downward
 285 moving block has dimension of $100 \times 150 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ for Panel 3 and dimension $100 \times 250 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ for
 286 Panel 4. Panel 5 is taller and characterized by the presence of three openings. It is 400 mm wide, 100 mm
 287 thick and 1300 mm high and is made of 105 blocks. The dimensions of the fictitious block are the same
 288 adopted in the Panel 4 case.

Figure 10. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Panel 3 case.

289 For Panel 3 and Panel 4, as expected, results show that collapse mechanism is affected by the portion of
 290 structure involved into settlement.

291 Figure 10 presents the mechanism obtained using the different models, referring to Panel 3. Results of
 292 LA and FEM, Figure 10a) and b), indicate that the masonry wall is almost stable with the separation of
 293 only one little macro-block which follows the downward movement of the settlement. The FEM simulation
 294 (Figure 9c) is in partial agreement with the results of the two previous methods, since the portion affected by
 295 the settlement is fairly larger. Nonetheless, apart from a slight localization of shear failure point on the first
 296 floor spandrel, it can be observed that the continuum model is able to reproduce the collapse configuration
 297 in which the settlement practically involves only the supported portion of the wall.

298 Figure 11 refers to Panel 4. The collapse mechanism obtained with LA, Figure 11a), caused the generation
 299 of three distinct macro-blocks separated by ‘stair-stepped’ cracks: the first one (1), positioned at ground
 300 level, remains stable, the second portion of the panels (2) follows, without crashing, the downward
 301 movement of the fictitious block and the third one (3), which corresponds to the portion of the panel
 302 upon the architrave of first opening, rotates without cracking around the upper left corner of the first
 303 macro-block. FEM/DEM, 9b), produces a similar collapse but the portion of the panel at first floor, unlike
 304 LA results, splits in two macro-block (3) and (4) with a almost symmetric mechanism if compared with that
 305 of ground level. FEM simulation results (Figure 9c) show a localization of the plastic points that reflects the

Figure 11. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Panel 4 case.

306 kinematics described above. In fact, failure involves the bottom spandrel at the end of the supported part,
 307 the first floor spandrel with prevalence of shear failure mechanisms and it is possible to see the formation
 308 of tensile failure points at the top left part of the wall, according to the mechanism obtained through a
 309 FEM/DEM approach.

Figure 12. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Panel 5 case.

310 Figure 12 refers to Panel 5. The different height of the panel does not influence the collapse mechanism
 311 obtained with LA and FEM, Figure 12a) and 12b), which results are similar to those obtained for Panel
 312 4. In particular, it may be observed the formation of three macro-blocks: portion (1) is stable, portion (2)
 313 follows the downward movement of the fictitious block and the portion (3) acts as a unique rigid body
 314 which rotates around the lower right corner of the macro-block (2). Furthermore the presence of two

315 openings seems that does not affects the collapse mechanism of this portion of the wall. Apart from the
 316 slight cracking occurring in the top spandrel, FEM results (9c) are in fair agreement with the observations
 317 reported above and the failure mechanism described by the plastic points is very similar to Panel 4 one.

318 3.3 Façades with opening

319 The collapse mechanism of two-storey and three-storey masonry façades characterized by different
 320 geometries is investigated. Façade 1 and Façade 2 have the same geometry and are characterized by the
 321 presence of four openings, two doors at the ground level and two windows at the first floor which have the
 322 same dimensions ($200 \times 350 \text{ mm}^2$). Each façade is 1500 mm wide, 50 mm thick and 1200 mm high, made
 323 of 320 blocks with dimensions $50 \times 100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$. The dimension of the fictitious block is $100 \times 300 \times 50$
 324 mm^3 for both the analysed cases. Façade 1 is affected by a lateral settlement, while Façade 2 to a central
 settlement.

Figure 13. a)LA, b)FEM/DEM and c)FEM results for Façade 1 case.

325

326 Figure 13 presents the collapse mechanism referring to Façade 1. LA, Figure 13a), and FEM/DEM,
 327 Figure 13b), present a similar mechanism with the façade splitted into two distinct portions. The right
 328 side, which is involved into settlement, presents the part (1) which is stable and follows the downward
 329 settlement movement, the part (2) which slightly rotates around the upper right corner of macro-block (1)
 330 without cracking, the rigid parts (3) and (4) in correspondence of the architraves of ground and first floor
 331 which exhibit both a hinging behaviour. The left side of façade, not involved into settlement, remain as
 332 expected stable. Interesting to notice is the presence of two diagonal cracks, starting from the upper left
 333 corner of the right door and the right window, which pass through all the central portion of the masonry
 334 façade. The continuum FEM approach (Figure 13c) is able to reproduce the failure pattern occurring in
 335 this case, and the results show that the most affected parts of the structure are the top right and the first
 336 floor spandrel, in which both tensile and shear failure occurs. Differently to what described by the two
 337 previous approaches, in the continuum FEM model a slight damage occurs also in the supported left part,
 338 but the kinematic described in Figure 13a) and b) reflects in the accumulation of tensile plastic points at
 339 the top of the façades, indicating a rotation of the top spandrel. Figure 14 shows the collapse mechanism
 340 of Façade 2. Also in this case, LA and FEM, Figure 14a) and Figure 14b), produce a similar collapse
 341 exhibiting an anti-symmetric mechanism with respect to the central portion of the structure. Macro-block
 342 (1), located upon the fictitious block, follows rigidly the settlement movement and consequently the part (2)
 343 moves downward, hinging and sliding, with the formation of several diagonal cracks which reach the two
 344 lateral sides of the façade. Here a macro-block (3), including portions of the two storey, rotates without
 345 cracking around the lower right corner of the lateral stable portion of the structure and the macro-block (4),
 346 corresponding to the portion upon the architrave of the first floor windows, hinges around the upper left
 347 corner of part (3). The symmetry of this failure mechanism is reflected in the plastic points pattern reported

Figure 14. a)LA, b)FEM/DEM and c)FEM results for Façade 2 case.

348 in Figure 13c). The downward movement of the central pier causes the shear failure of the spandrels while tensile failure is mainly concentrated at the lintel ends. Concluding, a three-storey structure, named

Figure 15. a) LA, b) FEM/DEM and c) FEM results for Façade 3 case.

349
 350 Façade 3, shown in Figure 15 and subjected to a foundation settlement at the right pier is analysed. The
 351 structure is characterized by the presence of six openings, two doors at ground level and four windows,
 352 two for each storey, all having 200 mm width and 350 mm height. The façade is 1500 mm wide, 50 mm
 353 thick and 1800 mm high. It is made of 480 blocks with dimensions $50 \times 100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$. The dimension
 354 of the fictitious block is $100 \times 300 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$. Figure 15 presents the collapse obtained with the different
 355 models. As for previously analysed cases, the mechanisms obtained with LA, Figure 15a), and FEM,
 356 Figure 15b), are in good agreement, being possible to identify the formation of similar macro-blocks:
 357 part (1), positioned upon the fictitious block, follows the downward movement of the settlement without
 358 cracking. The part (2) similarly follows the movement of the portion below with a slight sliding behavior
 359 and a more evident rotation around its lower right corner; part (3), corresponding to the portion of masonry
 360 upon the architrave of the right door at ground level, rotates rigidly as well as part (4) which includes
 361 a portion of masonry upon the architrave of the window at first floor and a portion of the lateral side of
 362 the façade at the second storey. Macro-block (5), corresponding to the final portion of masonry upon the
 363 architrave of the window at second floor, rotates around the lower left corner of the architrave. Interesting
 364 to notice, as for other façades, the presence of diagonal cracks passing through the central portion of the

365 façade, that originate in correspondence of the upper right corner of door and windows. From the analysis
366 of the collapse mechanism it is possible to notice also a little rigid rotation of the macro-block (6) and (7)
367 identified by those diagonal cracks. The left side of structure as well as the central wall at ground level
368 remain stable. FEM analysis results (Figure 13c) show a concentration of tensile failure points in the top
369 part of the wall, which is compatible with the formation of block 5 reported in the LA and FEM/DEM
370 results and its clock-wise rotation. As in the two previous cases, at collapse, only slight damage occurs
371 in the supported part of the structure, while tensile and shear cracking affects the right portion, above the
372 downward moving pier.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

373 This work presents the comparison of failure patterns characterizing the response of dry joints masonry
374 walls subjected to settlements. Three numerical formulations have been adopted: a Limit Analysis, a
375 FEM/DEM and FEM approach. The models have been briefly described and preliminary validated referring
376 to experimental and numerical literature results. A comparative study has then been performed, varying the
377 main factors affecting the response of masonry structures in case of settlements, that is wall dimensions,
378 presence of openings, extension of the settling area. All the models have proven to be very efficient from a
379 computational point of view and able to reproduce the collapse mechanisms, and can thus be considered a
380 useful tool to back-analyse real-scale problems in order to identify the causes of observed crack pattern or
381 to predict the damage distribution when a settlement is expected to occur, as in the case of underground
382 excavation or in case of natural triggering factors. The adoption of micro-models, i.e. Limit Analysis
383 and FEM/DEM, implies that the structure is described with its real texture, taking into account block
384 dimensions and the *internal structure* of the wall. While in most continuum approach this aspect is only
385 marginally considered, the FEM model adopted in this study is founded on a constitutive model in which
386 both joint orientations and block proportions are taken into account. A specific advantage of Limit Analysis
387 approach is the low number of parameters required to perform analysis, being friction and self-weight per
388 unit volume the only mechanical information needed. The same holds for the FEM model, but the elastic
389 parameters adopted need to be determined through a homogenization procedure in order to be assigned to
390 the continuum. The comparisons have been made on a total set of eight walls (if the benchmark cases are
391 excluded) and results have been compared in terms of crack pattern at collapse (LA and FEM/DEM) and
392 failure (plastic) points (FEM) in which either tensile or shear criterion is reached. In all the analysed cases
393 the models are in fair agreement, showing the strong influence of the extension of the settling area and of
394 the opening distribution. The cases of Panel 4 and Panel 5 have shown an almost negligible effect of the
395 panel height (over a certain slenderness of the structure) in case of localized settlement.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

396 MPE and MPI developed a novel feature of ALMA 2.0 to take into account the effect of foundation
397 settlement and performed the analysis with the LA approach. ER and MS carried out the analysis with
398 FEM/DEM and FEM approach respectively. All authors equally contributed to the common sections and
399 took care of the description of the adopted models. PT and GdF supervised the whole work during the
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